

Assessing Customer Choices for Herbal and Synthetic Skin Care Products Based on Advantages

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Abstract

Marketing professionals are keen to find out more information about consumers' using intentions in order to increase sales of their new or current products or services. In light of this, pertinent information about client intentions may be essential for making marketing decisions. Several factors affect the consumer's intention. The goal of this observation was to determine what factors people used to decide whether to buy herbal and synthetic skin care products offline or online. This study uses an exploratory survey approach. As a consequence, situational, psychological, personal, socio-cultural, marketing, and many other aspects were addressed, and the collected data was assessed using Microsoft Excel software. The statistical population includes everyone who uses the items in Bangladesh, Brazil, Canada, Egypt, Malaysia, and the United States. Since the sampling method utilized was random and the statistical population had no bounds, the sample size was set at 36. The information was gathered via a questionnaire with a five-option Likert scale and 11 items (both major and demographic). At the very least, the validity and reliability standards were met. The researchers received 50 completed questionnaires out of the original 36 surveys. There were two layers of descriptive and inferential data analysis. The results showed that each of the four factors significantly affected consumers' inclinations to utilize herbal or synthetic products in the research region.

I. Introduction

The rising trend of transitioning from non-organic to green cosmetics, driven by health and eco-friendliness considerations, adds a layer of complexity to skincare product preferences. Health consciousness leads consumers to scrutinize product ingredients, favoring natural and organic options that align with their health-oriented attitudes. Simultaneously, increased awareness of environmental issues and animal cruelty prompts ethical considerations, driving environmentally-conscious consumers towards organic products. While herbal skincare products gain ground, synthetic skincare products formulated with laboratory-derived ingredients also maintain their appeal, offering scientific innovation and efficacy. The credibility of scientifically proven ingredients reinforces consumer confidence in their potential

benefits. This highlights the diverse preferences within the skincare market, with some consumers valuing natural ingredients and others placing trust in scientifically-backed formulations. Understanding the intricacies of consumer behavior is pivotal, as it hinges on problem recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, the actual using decision, and post-uses behavior [12]. Motivation, both intrinsic and extrinsic, influences the extent of effort consumers invest in these stages. This study investigates how consumers perceive and assess the price of skincare items from these categories. By examining the influence of factors such as situational, psychological, personal, socio-cultural, marketing, and many other elements, this research aims to uncover the intricate dynamics driving consumer decision-making in the skincare market [14].

II. Literature Review

Factors contributing to the decision-making:

In the dynamic world of the skincare industry, consumer decision-making plays a pivotal role in determining market trends. As consumers become more discerning and conscious about the products they use, their decision-making process is increasingly influenced by a plethora of factors.

i. Perceived functional value:

One such factor is the perceived functional value, which stems from product safety, uniqueness, usability, reliability, and durability [13]. Consumer preferences are indirectly influenced by functional value, aligning with the financial pragmatic theory. This theory asserts that consumers make choices based on maximizing their benefits within the constraints of their financial resources and circumstances. In essence, consumers prioritize their spending in a way that aligns with their financial constraints while aiming to fulfill their needs and desires [3]. If the functional value fulfills a consumer's requirements for product quality and capabilities, it facilitates the realization of their desires. Decision-making hinges on the consumers' demands for functional value, with higher perceptions of this value leading to stronger use intentions [13].

ii. Symbolic value:

The second factor, symbolic value, encompasses social approval, self-expression, conspicuousness, and prestige. Aspects such as the product's significance and image contribute to the characterization of symbolic value [3]. The products they choose and the brands they associate with become part of their identity narrative, influencing how they are perceived by others and how they perceive themselves. Symbolic values also hold importance for consumers as they align their behavior with the roles they occupy in society (Fajardo & Tsiros) [6]. Consumers may use a product to gain acceptance within a specific social group or conform to societal norms. Through consumption behavior and affiliations with reference groups, consumers achieve self-improvement and access to social value. By mirroring the consumption patterns or impressions of a reference group, consumers

identify with that group. Consequently, a higher perceived symbolic value correlates with stronger using decisions.

iii. Experiential value:

The level of knowledge held by consumers, be it intrinsic or extrinsic, plays a crucial role. Park, Mothersbaugh, and Feick [2] categorize knowledge into subjective, objective, and experience-based types, encompassing consumer experiences, provided information, and past product usage.

One of them, experiential value, pertains to the emotions consumers associate with the consumption of goods or services. Experiential values are basically the benefits consumers derive from products in terms of their emotional responses. In certain situations, emotional judgments are swift predictors, causing consumers to assess products or services based on immediate emotional cues. Generally, these values manifest positively, such as brand loyalty, or negatively, as negative word-of-mouth [3]. The more positive the evaluation, the greater the likelihood of a purchase intention.

Herbal and synthetic products:

i. Ethical consumerism:

Nowadays, consumers are transitioning from non-organic to green cosmetics, reflecting the momentum of ethical consumerism. A study by Kim and Seock [1] shows that consumers today favor products that prioritize health and eco-friendliness, with both factors interplaying in their purchasing behavior. But what is the driving force behind?

The personal value, health consciousness, serves as a guiding force for individuals when making decisions related to adopting healthy behaviors [7]. For example, consumers highly focused on health and safety might meticulously assess product ingredients prior to consumption compared to those with lower health consciousness [4]. A case in point is the brand Aveda, which employs a slogan emphasizing product safety and its relation to health: Would you prefer petroleum-based moisturizer? According to [8], "What you put on your body should be just as natural and healthy as what you put in it.". This slogan underscores the significance of topical application to the body in parity with dietary choices. Given that natural beauty products often exclude harmful

chemicals like Sodium Laureth Sulfate (SLES), diethanolamine (DEA), and preservatives derived from formaldehyde, consumers with health consciousness are likely to favor organic skin and hair care products due to their health-oriented attitudes [9].

A parallel increase in awareness regarding animal cruelty in product testing has prompted ethical considerations by both companies and consumers toward living beings and the environment. Environmentally-conscious consumers tend to adjust their purchasing habits to align with environmental well-being [10]. Addressing concerns about environmental harm stemming from hazardous substances and animal testing, the personal care industry has introduced organic products manufactured without pesticides, synthetic chemicals, and animal testing [11]. Furthermore, some companies have adopted recyclable packaging, indicating a concern for disposal issues. Thus, environmental consciousness significantly shapes consumer behavior towards organic products [5]. It is reasonable to posit that a consumer's environmental awareness is positively correlated with their intention to use organic beauty products.

ii. Synthetic skincare products:

On the other hand, synthetic skin care products, formulated with laboratory-derived ingredients, have become integral components of modern consumer preferences as well. These products offer a unique blend of scientific innovation and product efficacy. The scientifically proven effectiveness of ingredients resonates with consumers seeking visible results. Hyaluronic acid, for instance, known for its remarkable ability to retain moisture and plump the skin, addresses specific skincare concerns such as hydration, fine lines, and skin texture. Overall, scientific foundation supporting the benefits of such ingredients reinforces consumer confidence in their potential outcomes.

Buying behavior:

i. Marketing stimuli:

In essence, marketing, or marketing communication, is a procedure that organizations undertake to interact and engage in conversations with their

diverse audiences. To achieve this, organizations devise, deliver, and assess messages aimed at specific groups of stakeholders. The primary goal of marketing communications is to influence how a company and its offerings are perceived, understood, and acted upon by its intended audience.

Consumers are surrounded by all kinds of marketing stimuli that, in one way or another, affect their buying behavior. According to [11], through advertising, a company can exert influence over consumers by either providing information about its products and services or reminding them of these offerings. Advertising also serves the purpose of persuading consumers and aiding them in distinguishing a product or company from competitors within a specific market. Furthermore, it is highlighted that advertising can be employed to establish a long-term brand image or generate rapid sales. Additionally, the mere presence of extensive advertising may boost sales, as consumers tend to associate heavily advertised brands with good value and higher quality, making them more inclined to use.

The theory underpinning advertising, which posits that it can impact consumers' knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors, remains a subject of controversy. Advertising can indeed convince consumers to buy a product they have never used before. However, in accordance with the weak theory of advertising, consumers' buying habits and purchasing patterns are more influenced by habit than exposure to advertisements. In other words, the weak theory of advertising suggests that people primarily pay attention to ads for products they are already familiar with or have prior knowledge of, such as products they are already using or have heard of. The decision to try a new product can be triggered not only by advertising but also by factors such as retail availability and word-of-mouth recommendations.

In addition to advertising, another component of marketing communications that influences consumer behavior is sales promotion. Sales promotion aims to provide consumers with extra value as an incentive to spur an immediate purchase. Various sales promotion methods exist, such as coupons, contests, and premiums. What these techniques have in common is that they all provide a stimulus or reward that entices consumers, who receive promotional

messages, to make a purchase today instead of postponing it to the next day or week. The additional value offered with the product is intended to motivate consumers to buy the product sooner rather than later.

ii. Consumer purchasing decisions step-by-step:

Understanding consumer behavior involves gaining insight into how consumers make purchasing decisions. The consumer decision-making process commences when an individual recognizes the need to make a purchase to fulfill a specific requirement. This process begins with problem recognition and encompasses four subsequent stages: information search, evaluation of alternatives, the actual uses decision, and post-use behavior.

The extent of effort a consumer invests in this process largely hinges on the significance of the matter at hand. In other words, it depends on the consumer's motivation to allocate time and energy to address a particular need.

Consumer motivation, as per the expectancy theory, is predominantly driven by cognitive factors rather than biological ones. This theory posits that consumer behavior is guided by the expectation of achieving specific desired outcomes. In essence, behavior is not compelled from within but is instead influenced by the anticipation of more favorable outcomes from choosing one product over another.

Consumer uses invariably result from the identification of a problem or need. The consumer decision-making process commences with the recognition of a disparity between the consumer's current state and the desired ideal state, which signifies a problem that needs resolution. This ideal state the consumer strives for is referred to as a goal.

Problem recognition can occur in two ways: need recognition and opportunity recognition. Need recognition arises when a person's current state deteriorates without a purchase, such as running out of wrinkle cream. Conversely, opportunity recognition occurs when the ideal state can be elevated, and better-quality products are available. In both cases, the trigger for problem recognition is the awareness of a gap between the current and ideal states.

Needs can be categorized into two basic types: biogenic and psychogenic needs. Biogenic needs, such as those for food, water, air, and shelter, are inherent and essential for sustaining life. Psychogenic needs, on the other hand, encompass desires for status, power, and affiliation, which are culturally acquired and reflect societal priorities. In the context of facial skin care products, psychogenic needs play a significant role in consumer behavior.

The manner in which a need is satisfied depends on an individual's cultural environment, learning experiences, and personal history. This specific way of fulfilling a need is referred to as a want. For example, two individuals with a similar need for facial cream may pursue different products—one may prioritize cost, while another may prioritize the perceived benefits, regardless of the cost.

Problem or need recognition can arise from internal or external stimuli. Internal stimuli are innate needs, such as hunger or thirst, which, when reaching a certain threshold, become driving forces for consumer uses. External stimuli, on the other hand, are triggered by external factors, such as admiring a friend's designer clothes or skin care products, prompting thoughts about making a purchase.

Marketing efforts often encourage problem recognition. Advertisers frequently attempt to create new needs or problems for consumers, initiating the decision-making process by either presenting a new ideal state or making consumers dissatisfied with their current state. This is often achieved through "before" and "after" imagery to motivate consumers to seek a solution to achieve the new ideal state, a tactic commonly employed in facial skin care product advertising.

Following problem recognition, consumers must seek information to address the issue. Two primary types of information searches are identified: heightened attention and active information search. Heightened attention involves consumers becoming more observant of information, advertisements, peer uses, and conversations related to the subject. Active information search, conversely, entails consumers actively seeking information through reading, research, or discussions with friends.

This deliberate search for information from external sources follows an initial internal search from the

consumer's own memory. Consumers often have stored information from past experiences that can be used to find a solution to the problem. However, internal search is usually supplemented by external search as consumers explore various sources, such as friends, advertisements, and media, to gather information. The extent of external search conducted depends on motivation, existing knowledge, and the ease of obtaining additional information.

Consumers access information from four primary sources: personal sources (friends, family, colleagues), commercial sources (advertising, sales personnel, displays), public sources (mass media, consumer organizations), and experiential sources (product examination and usage). Commercial sources are the most common information providers, while personal sources tend to have the greatest impact. The effectiveness of each source varies based on consumer characteristics and the product category.

The information search that occurs after problem recognition and relates to specific data about the issue is termed pre-uses search. Additionally, consumers often engage in ongoing search, continuously seeking information on a particular topic. This behavior may involve perusing catalogs or magazines without an immediate intention to use.

After acquiring information on how to address the problem, consumers must evaluate the available alternatives and decide which one to choose. This evaluation of alternatives is typically the phase in the decision-making process that demands the most effort from consumers. In some cases, an abundance of alternatives can complicate the decision-making process.

The alternatives actively considered by a consumer during the evaluation are referred to as the evoked set. This set comprises products the consumer is already familiar with and can readily recall when assessing various options. It encompasses both preferred and disfavored brands. After careful consideration, consumers make their final decisions.

This study aims to demonstrate how consumers evaluate both herbal and synthetic skincare products and determine what key factors contribute the most.

The following hypotheses have been developed in relation to the facts listed below:

- 1.1** The marketing significantly influences consumers' intentions to utilize herbal skin care products.
- 1.2** The intention to use synthetic skin care products is significantly impacted by the marketing.
- 2.1** Socio-cultural aspects significantly influence consumers' intentions to utilize herbal skin care products.
- 2.2** Socio-cultural variables significantly affect people's intentions to utilize artificial skin care products.
- 3.1** The inclination to utilize herbal skin care products is significantly influenced by situational circumstances.
- 3.2** The inclination to utilize synthetic skin care products is significantly impacted by situational variables.
- 4.1** Personal psychological variables have a big impact on whether someone plans to utilize herbal skin care products.
- 4.2** Psychological aspects of an individual's personality have a big impact on whether they plan to utilize synthetic skin care products.

III. Research Methodologies

Statistical Population and sampling method

Consumers of herbal and synthetic skin care products are included in the statistical population in Bangladesh, Brazil, Canada, Egypt, Malaysia, Kazakhstan, and the USA. Using the Morgan's table, the sample size was determined. 36 individuals were ultimately chosen as the sample size, and they were picked at random. The attrition rate was projected to be 11.6% since it is an issue. 10 persons were therefore included in the sample.

Instrumentation

As the anticipated attrition rate was added to the sample, a total of 50 questionnaires were delivered. 36 completed and gave the researchers one of the questionnaires. The exam has 4 items for herbal and synthetic options, and 3 things for personal traits. From fully agree (1 value) to entirely disagree (5 value), the items contained 5 choice-options on the Likert scale. The test's reliability and validity are assessed. The test's 2.44 and 2.98 validity

indices, which are excellent in terms of qualitative evaluation and the values correspond to the usage of herbal and synthetic skin care products were obtained, as shown in **tables 2, 3, 4, and 5** respectively. The Cronbach Alpha was employed to assess the test's dependability, and the findings are shown in **table 1**.

Table 1. Reliability coefficients of the test (Cronbach's Alpha)

Herbal		Synthetic
0.627591	Total	0.568166

Table 1 shows that all the values fall between poor and questionable. The factorial analysis was used to examine all the items' validity, and the results revealed good factorial loading (meaning more than 0.05) in this regard.

To obtain the relevant data in terms of the variables, the applicable research design is a descriptive survey. The study was conducted online. The outcomes can be used to enhance business operations and financial procedures.

Data analysis

The methodologies utilized to examine the data were descriptive and inferential. Numerous participants were in the 15-34 age range, and the majority of the group from Bangladesh, according to demographic data. However, the majority of the group had no personal income, as many of them were students, and thus were reliant in this respect.

Figure 1: Population Age.

Figure 2: Population Demographic.

Table 2. Results of single t-test for herbal skin care products (N=36)

Variables	Mean	SD	Df	T	P Value
Marketing	2.444	1.275	35	-2.61456	0.013089
Socio-cultural	3.444	1.230	35	2.169304	0.036936
Situational	3.333	1.014	35	1.972026	0.056550
Psychological	2.194	1.238	35	-3.904279	0.000411
Total	11.416	3.280		15.392131	0.000000

Table 2 shows that all the t statistics for the usage of herbal skin care products are significant. The values and the outcomes can be viewed as evidence supporting or refuting the alternative hypothesis. In reality, every relevant hypothesis has been rejected as the null hypothesis.

Table 3. Results of single t-test for synthetic skin care products (N= 36)

Variables	Mean	SD	Df	T	P Value
Marketing	2.389	1.253	35	-2.925	0.006002
Socio-cultural	3.25	1.278	35	1.174	0.248246
Situational	2.722	1.044	35	-1.597	0.119314
Psychological	2.666	1.054	35	-1.898	0.066054
Total	11.027	3.069		15.697	0.000000

Table 3 shows that all t statistics are significant in terms of synthetic usage (P-value = 0.0), as can be shown. In actuality, the operational hypotheses have been rejected as the null hypothesis.

Table 4. Results of Fridman test and variable's preference herbal skin care products (N=36)

Variables	Df	F(t)	Critical Value	Chi Square	P Value
All 4	3	13473.542	7.815	0.00	0.00

Table 4 shows the statistics that were utilized to determine if all the elements (P-value = 0.00) have not a significant influence and to decide the propensity to use herbal skin care products.

Table 5. Results of Fridman test and variable's preference synthetic skin care products (N=36)

Variables	Df	F(t)	Critical Value	Chi Square	P Value
All 4	3	13130.209	7.815	0.00	0.00

Table 5 shows the statistical approach that was used to demonstrate that all the elements (P-value = 0.00) have not a significant influence in influencing and molding the using intention for synthetic skin care products.

The study's findings included information on the impact of sectional characteristics such age, gender, and income, as shown in **figures 1 and 2** respectively. Age, and financial level do not significantly influence the use of skin care products, according to Kruskal-Wallis data. Additionally, a non-significant gender effect was noted. Although it is reasonable to anticipate that gender, age, and income will have a major impact on customers' using intentions, in the study, neither a significant impact nor evidence of this was discovered.

IV. Conclusion

A competitive market might be appealing to customers because the majority of the study's participants were dependent on income. It is advised that businesses make things that are tailored to the components since the mixed effects of marketing are crucial in determining purchasing intention. Being honest in advertising is a crucial component in gaining the confidence of people. In other words, when there is no indication that they are high quality and effective, they should either withdraw or act as though they are. Being focused in this area is another crucial aspect of product reviews. In a cutthroat and expanding industry, pricing is an additional crucial element. Situational factors, such as those identified in the study and others (such as holidays, special

occasions, and Black Friday deals), are also significant. For instance, physical stores, internet stores, and seasonal variables might influence consumers' intentions in this respect. To ensure a company's success, socio-cultural aspects and paying attention to product feedback are crucial. The other factors in terms of using intention are variables like personality and psychological traits that have been confirmed as determining for a phenomenon known as impulsive shopping (making irrational, rash purchases motivated by their immediate emotional responses rather than a careful, rational evaluation of the good or need). It should be noted that no items in this sector may be promoted, and women cannot demonstrate how the products are used or their effects on consumers of herbal skin care products. This is especially true of the advertising portion of the herbal and synthetic skin care market. The only components that may really be promoted in the nation are synthetic and those that prevent color-tune and other dermatological issues.

V. Limitations

The results of this study can only be applied to Bangladesh, Brazil, Canada, Egypt, Malaysia, Kazakhstan, and USA, hence caution should be taken when extrapolating them. The absence of subculture and individuals as an independent variable is another drawback.

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